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Research Article

**MEDICAL CONSULTATION, TRENDS OF FASTING, DIETARY
PATTERN & SLEEP AMONG FEMALES WITH PREGNANCY
BEFORE RAMADAN**¹Dr. Azhar Waqas Zareef, ²Dr. Muhammad Talha, ³Dr. Muhammad Usman Zaib¹DHQ Hospital Toba Tek Singh²City (Gyane) Hospital, Toba Tek Singh³Rural Health Center 316 GB, Toba Tek Singh

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Abstract:

Objective: This research work aimed to check the before Ramadan medical consultation, dietary pattern, trends of fasting and cycle of sleep among females having pregnancy.

Methodology: This is a transverse research work based on observations. This research work carried out from March 2018 to June 2018 at tertiary health care center in Lahore. Interview was the main tool to collect the information on a well-organized questionnaire. Total two hundred and seventy nine females with pregnancy who were regularly observing fast in the month of Ramadan were the part of this research work. **Results:** Total one hundred and ninety eight (85.70%) females were observing fast from 1-10 days. Approximately, two hundred and two (72.40%) never visited any physician for before Ramadan advice about the fasting impact in the period of pregnancy. Females with pregnancy 81.70% (n: 228) found with belief that there is no impact of fasting on the development of fetal in their body, whereas one hundred and nineteen (42.70%) members of family were fearing regarding the health on unborn child and pregnant females. Total 74.0% (n: 208) females with pregnancy were available with decreased sleep cycle of three to four hours. Most of the females utilized the eatables full of fat & carbohydrates at the time of Sehri & Iftar.

Conclusions: Before Ramadan medical advice about the safety during fast in the period of pregnancy should be a part of structure and it should be necessary for pregnant females and their families. The lapses in awareness as diagnosed by this research work may provide support to the professionals of the health care field to tackle this issue.

KEYWORDS: Fasting, consultation, necessary, pregnant, carbohydrates, fats, methodology.

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INTRODUCTION:

Muslims do not eat and drink from sunrise to sunset in the month of Ramadan which is the 9th month in the Islamic calendar [1, 2]. The duration of fasting is different in different areas of countries as well as world depending upon the geography and seasons and its duration can be from twelve hours to nineteen hours [3]. Hindrance to take water can lead to dehydration, high viscosity of blood & hypotension in the summer season [4-6] & it can lead to the danger of preterm delivery if observance of fast carried out before twenty week of gestation period [7]. Holy Quran has mentioned the exemption from fasting for ill persons or travelers. There are verses available in Holy Quran regarding the fasting [8]. It is very obvious in the Hadith that female with pregnancy has exemption from observing fast if she frightens that fast will lead to a harm to her health or the health of her unborn child [9-12].

Regardless of the exemptions in the months of pregnancy most of the females observe fasting. Medical professionals confronted with the issue that whether to advice about fasting in Ramadan or not in the duration of pregnancy. Cultural sensitivity is very important for tackle of this issue by the physician. Then he will be well-informed about the teaching of religion and instruction about observe fasting in the duration of pregnancy and medical administration of dysglycaemia associated with fasting. This was a

transverse research work based upon observations and the aim was to determine the before Ramadan consultation behavior, trend of fasting, dietary habits and sleeps cycle among females having pregnancy.

METHODOLOGY:

This research work carried out from March 2018 to June 2018 at department of gynecology in Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore. We got the willing of each pregnant female who were participating in the casework. A well-organized questionnaire base on interview was the main tool for the collection of information from the subjects of this study. The calculation of the size of sample carried out from online raosoft.com by ninety five percent confidence interval & 5.0% of error of margin needed for the samples of two hundred and seventy nine. The ethical committee of the same hospital gave the approval for the conduction of this research work. The pregnant females who were fasting in Ramadan were the part of this research work.

RESULTS:

Two hundred and seventy nine females were the part of this research work. The average age of the pregnant females was 25.90 ± 5.10 year with arrange of 16-40 years. The level of education was less than ten years in 166 (59.5%) & ninety eight percent pregnant females were housewives. Most common language was Saraiki 32.970% (n: 92), Sindhi 31.9% (n: 89) & Urdu 26.9% (n: 75) (Table-1).

Table-I: Demographic Features of study population (n = 279).

Demographic Characteristics		Frequency	Percent
Age Group	16-25 years	156.0	55.900%
	26-35 years	112.0	40.100%
	36-45 years	11.0	3.900%
Education	Primary education	166.0	59.500%
	Matric	61.0	21.860%
	Intermediate	39.0	13.980%
	Graduate	13.0	4.660%
Profession	Religious scholar	1.0	0.350%
	Housewife	274.0	98.200%
	Nurse	2.0	0.710%
	Tailor	1.0	0.350%
	Teacher	1.0	0.350%
Language	Balochi	92.0	32.970%
	Sindhi	89.0	31.900%

Saraiki	2.0	0.720%
Urdu	75.0	26.880%
Punjabi	9.0	3.230%
Pashto	12.0	4.300%

Most of the pregnant females 63.40% (n: 177) were prim-gravida. Most of the pregnant females 70.0% (n: 195) visited outpatient department for the very first time in the last 3 months of the period of pregnancy. Though, most of females with pregnancy observed fast in Ramadan 82.80% (n: 231), 85.70% (n: 198) observed fast for one to ten days. Interview of these females carried out in the month of Ramadan regardless of their period of pregnancy. The average days of fasting were 5.55 ± 7.96 .

All the trends of fasting are available in Table-2 with the percentage and number of the pregnant females in each trend.

Table-II: Fasting Trends (n = 279).

Fasting Trends		Frequency	Percent
Gravidity	Primary gravid	177.0	63.400%
	Multi gravid	102.0	36.500%
Period of Gestation	1st Trimester	11.0	3.900%
	2nd Trimester	73.0	26.200%
	3rd Trimester	195.0	69.900%
Fasting during pregnancy	No	48.0	17.200%
	Yes	231.0	82.800%
Number of days of women fasted	1-10 days	198.0	85.700%
	11-20 days	11.0	4.800%
	21-30 days	22.0	9.500%

Reason for not fasting (n = 48)	Feeling of weakness	39.0	81.200%
	The unborn child may be under-weight	1.0	2.100%
	Family members advising not to fast	2.0	420.000%
	Health care providers advising not to fast	6.0	12.500%
Pre-Ramadan Medical Consultation for fasting	No	202.0	72.400%
	Yes	77.0	27.600%
If yes, by whom (n=77)	We know it better	9.0	11.000%
	Doctor	10.0	12.900%
	Nurse	7.0	9.090%
	Muslim Scholars	23.0	29.800%
	Family Members	28.0	36.300%
Reason for not consulting in pre-Ramadan period (n=202)	Unaware of its importance	185.0	91.500%
	Doctor will not allow for fasting	17.0	8.500%
Did Doctor Allow to fast (n=77)	No	24.0	31.200%
	Yes	53.0	68.800%

Weakness was the main reason to leave fast in 81.20% (n: 39) pregnant females. The beliefs about fasting are available in Table-3 with the percentage of females with pregnancy as well as their quantity for each category.

Table-III: Beliefs regarding fasting (n = 279)

Beliefs		Frequency	Percent
Beliefs regarding fasting in pregnancy	Farz (Compulsory)	265.0	95.700%
	Sunnah	4.0	1.400%
	Fasting is not necessary. (If we fast it will give reward. If do not fast then there is no Gunnah (Punishment)	8.0	2.900%
Mother who breastfeed, should they fast?	No	30.0	10.800%
	Yes	244.0	87.500%
	Don't Know	5.0	1.800%
Do you think that pregnant women should fast during Ramadan?	No	14.0	5.000%
	Yes	265.0	95.000%
Why it is harmful to fast during pregnancy?	Your health	7.0	2.500%
	Health of your unborn child	22.0	7.900%
	Harmful to both of you	21.0	7.500%
	It will not cause any harm	228.0	81.700%
	Any other	1.0	0.350%
Is fasting during pregnancy difficult?	No	117.0	41.900%
	Yes	162.0	58.100%
Why it is difficult? (n=162)	You feel very weak	60.0	37.000%
	Feel more hungry	51.0	31.500%
	Feel more thirsty	37.0	22.800%
	Feel more sleepy	14.0	8.600%
Fears of spouse about fasting in pregnancy	She will be weak	154.0	55.200%
	Fear of harm to health of fetus	6.0	2.200%
	The health of mother and unborn child could be effected	119.0	42.700%
Do fetal movement decrease during fasting?	No	97.0	34.800%
	Yes	99.0	35.500%
	Don't know	83.0	29.700%

About 81.70% (n: 228) females found with the belief that fasting cannot harm to their child as well as their health. But 42.70% (n: 119) members of family were worry about the health of fetal as well as mother. We found no important disparity in the movement of fetal in the fasting period as well as after Iftar in 29.70% females with pregnancy. Most common utilized beverage was tea by 54.0% (n: 124) females. About 67.0% (n: 155) females were preferring the opening of fast with sharbat whereas 27.0% (n: 62) females were using dates to open the fast, but the diet item which were very common in Aftar were fruit chaat used by 83.0% (n: 192), fried diet by 72.0% (n: 167), chick peas 64.0% (n: 148) and dahi-baray 60.0% (n: 139).

DISCUSSION:

A majority of the females with pregnancy was observing fast of Ramadan regardless of exemption in religious teachings [9-12]. This can lead to a dangerous situation. There are puzzling views of the professionals of health care field for this issue. In this research work, most of the females were observing fast from one to ten days. Large number of days were the reason of weakness among females. This result is same with the finding of Sultan IE in which 50.0% females quit fasting because of weakness while one research work showed the percentage as 51.20% [13, 14]. Parity was also affecting the fasting in Ramadan as 63.40% pregnant females were prim-gravidas, whereas research work from Iran & Singapore display females with greater parity who were observing fast in the month of Ramadan [13, 15].

Majority of females with pregnancy 29.80% consulted the scholars of religious field to know about the safety of Ramadan fasting which is much greater than the practice available in United States of America [16]. 11.0% females felt themselves independent to decide whether to observe fast or not. This issue is also matter of concern for the professionals of the health care field for the safety of fetal and maternal health. In the research work of Robinson, only 3.0% females with pregnancy said that they had their personal doctor and they were able to decide this matter in a better way [17]. While in this research work, only 13.0% pregnant females showed their trust on the professionals of health care field.

Majority of females (95.70%) were aware about the proper awareness of the principles of Islam but they were not aware about the exemption. Mubeen in his research work [18] stated that majority of females (54.0%) were available with only formal education & 88.0% among them were considering the fasting in the month of Ramadan as their obligatory duty. Majority of pregnant females (81.70%) found with the belief that the observation of fast was dangerous for their as well as health of fetal and different research works concluded that there was no impact of fasting in the month of Ramadan on the health of fetal or neonate [19, 20]. Khoshdel A reported in his research work the high frequency of preterm labor & restriction in the development in the mothers who were observing fast but that research work was available with a small size of sample & for a very short duration [21]. We observed no important disparity in the movement of fetal during fast and after the Iftar. In the same manner, a research work concluded that 97.0% females felt no impact on the movement of fetal [22, 23].

Deprivation in the sleep of mother is the main reason of the preterm birth & prematurity which is also the main important reason of the perinatal morbidity as well as mortality [24]. In the month of Ramadan, persons from different social & cultural upbringings have various preferences of diet consisting of high amounts of fats & carbohydrates [25]. The most important tool for the measurement of movement of fetal is CTG which was not in use of this research work. We saw the type of diet in this research work but did not count the calories level. The findings of this research work needs more evidences for the consolidation of general public.

CONCLUSION:

Before Ramadan clinical consultation is necessary for the health of fetal & mother. Proper advice about diet, proper sleep cycle and proper medication can decrease the risks for abnormalities. This will be a good step from the health care authorities to handle the situation.

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